

DISCOURSE ON GOOD GOVERNANCE: A BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS

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Abstract

Purpose: This study aims to discuss Good Governance, analyzed through the bibliometric approach with the Scopus database written by researchers from throughout the world from 2000 to 2021 and visualized through the VOS viewer software version 1.6.16. **Methods:** We conducted a bibliometric and content analysis of publication in the Scopus database. They were classified by publication year, authors, co authors, country, keywords, and journal title. We only retrieved articles written in English. We conducted content analysis using the VOS viewer software and visualized the co-occurrence of keywords and bibliographic coupling of sources and countries. **Results:** Following the study protocol, we found 539 articles on Good Governance over the past 22 years. The most productive journal that published these articles was International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change (n = 14). The post productive country were the United Kingdom (n = 215). Based on citations, the most influential authors, and journals were M. Lockwood (n = 292), and Journal of Business Ethics (n = 8098), respectively. The keywords of research on good governance formed 8 clusters (e.g good governance, governance, good corporate governance, performance, Indonesia, evidence). **Conclusion:** From a global perspective, Good Governance research in the past two decades has increased significantly. There were European published journals dominated publications. Thus, Asian country needs to conduct more active research on this topic.

Keywords: Bibliometric; Good Governance

Introduction

Background/rationale: This article discusses the discourse good governance during the last two decades (2000-2021). The discourse understanding is inseparable from bibliometric analysis (Lee, 2020; Mifrah et al., 2020; Omoregbe et al., 2020; Saravanan & Dominic, 2014), referring to the incorporation of various frameworks and methods to analyze citations from scientific publications. Such attempt leads to the development of different metrics to gain insight into the intellectual structure of a broad academic discipline and to evaluate the impact of a particular field of study (Akhavan et al., 2016; Putera, Suryanto, et al., 2020).

Objectives: This aim of this article was to provide useful data for understanding global publication trends regarding good governance. This study aimed to analyze the bibliographic characteristics and trends of articles on good governance published in journals indexed in Scopus written by researchers from throughout the world from 2000 to 2021 and to conduct an analysis of keyword co-occurrence using VOS viewer.

Methods

Ethics statement: This study did not involve human subjects; therefore, neither institutional review board approval nor informed consent was needed.

Study design: This study was a descriptive and bibliometric analysis based on a literature database.

Data sources: The data in this study were retrieved from the Scopus database. To obtain the necessary data, this study used the keyword “good governance” in the title, abstracts, and author’s keywords. We also limited the searching criteria by only including articles in the last 22 years (2000 – 2021). In this step, we found 539 articles. In the next step, we downloaded the articles from the scopus database and analyzed the 539 articles that had been sorted by relevance. In this study, the metadata and refined Scopus result values were retrieved in the RIS dataset format. However, before the bibliometric analysis, the consistency and reliability of the data were checked to address issues such as a lack of consistency in country names and keywords. The data were also standardized to ensure consistency regarding key words that sometimes appeared in singular or plural, abbreviations, or other forms.

Visualization: The data obtained from the Scopus database were analyzed using VOSviewer software, and simple statistics were calculated using Microsoft Excel.

Results

Based on a search with the keyword “good governance”, the result showed approximately 539 documents. Most articles were listed under social sciences (n = 232, 43%), business, management and accounting (n = 140, 26%), medicine (n = 34, 6%), economic, econometrics, and finance (n = 26, 5%), and environmental science (n = 23, 4%). The full distribution of Good Governance articles across the top 10 subject areas is shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Distribution of Good Governance based on subject area.

Figure 2: The most production journals based on the number of publications

Figure 3: Top 10 countries with publication of good governance

According to VOSviewer, the articles were published in 335 different journals. The highest number of articles were published in International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change, with 14 publications, followed by Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems (n = 10), Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences (n = 10), Trustee : the journal for hospital governing boards (n = 10), and International Journal of Public Administration (n = 8). The other most productive journals with the most publications are shown in Fig. 2. There were three journals each from United Kingdom and United States, two journals from India, and one journal each from Italy and Netherlands.

Figure 4: The most influential authors and source based on citation analysis

Figure 5: The most influential source based on citation analysis.

In the period 2000 to 2021, the United Kingdom was the country with the most publications on good governance, with 215 articles, followed by the United States with 106 articles. India, Malaysia, and Pakistan were the Asian countries ranked in the top 10 countries in terms of the most good governance publications. These three Asian countries ranked three, five and ninth, respectively. The top 10 countries can be seen in Fig. 3.

Fig. 4. the most influential authors based on citations recorded by the Scopus database. The most influential author was M. Lockwood, with 292 citations, followed D.C. Esty (n = 196), M. Abednego (n = 186), K. Kanagaretnam (n = 145), and M. Doornbos (n = 132). Fig. 5. present the influential source (i.e journals) based on citations. Journal of Business Ethics (n = 8098) was the most influential journal, followed by Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems (n = 2078), International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research (n = 1512), International Journal of Applied Business and Economic Research (n = 906), and International Journal of Public Administration (n = 606).

A content analysis was performed of the 539 publications sorted by relevance. Next, we performed a co-occurrence analysis with VOSviewer, using the “all keyword” analysis unit and the “full counting” method. We limited the frequency of keyword occurrence to 4 times; out of 1490 keywords VOSviewer found 71 keywords that met the threshold. The results of this analysis are presented in Fig. 6.

Figure 6: Network visualization of Good Governance

Good Governance (267), Governance (98), and Good Corporate Governance (49) were the top three keywords that appeared most frequently. Moreover, we found 9 clusters in this analysis. Fig. 4 shows these keywords divided into 9 clusters (each with a different number of keywords), which are represented by colors. The first cluster (red, 14 keywords) focused on Good Corporate Governance (49 occurrence), Performance (33 occurrence), and Indonesia (24 occurrence). The second cluster (green, 14 keywords) centered on Good Governance (267 occurrence), development (20 occurrence), and principle (15 occurrence). The third cluster (blue, 9 keywords) related to Governance (98 occurrence), Better Governance (14 occurrence), and Regulation (8 occurrence). The fourth cluster (yellow, 8 keywords) related to Implementation (15 occurrence), Implication (9 occurrence), and Good Governance Practice (5 occurrence). The fifth cluster (purple, 8 keywords) focused on case (17 occurrence), Model (16 occurrence), and practice (15 occurrence). The sixth cluster (light blue, 6 keywords) dealt with Analysis (17 occurrence), democracy (11 occurrence), and relationship (9 occurrence). The seventh cluster (orange, 5 keywords) focused on Impact (16 occurrence), Country (14 occurrence), and Institution (11 occurrence). The eighth cluster (brown, 4 keywords) focused on Evidence (23 occurrence), Better Corporate Governance (4 occurrence), and Toward Good Governance (4 occurrence). The ninth cluster (lavender, 3 keywords) focused on Role (20 occurrence), System (20 occurrence), and Good University Governance (9 occurrence).

Fig. 7 shows an overlay visualization of the Good Governance literature with the average number of publications from 2012 to 2018. There was a shift in topics; around 2012, the literature on good governance contained extensive discussions of the terms “good

governance”, “governance”, and “evidence”, and then the last 3 years discussed “good corporate governance”, “performance”, and “indonesia”.

Figure 7: Overlay visualization of Good Governance articles.

Discussion

Interpretation: Based on data from Scopus, the publication trends, journal performance, content analysis, and bibliographic coupling of countries and sources were analysed for research on good governance issues throughout the world. The current study focused on articles published in good governance. This study aimed to provide information on the status of publications in these fields. A total of 539 studies published were recorded in the scopus database. The data showed the rapidity of article publications and the responsiveness of researchers in analyzing on good governance around the world. However, limited research from a global perspective on good governance in the past 3 years has discussed good governance and its relationship with performance within the scope of social science.

Based on Fig. 3, the most productive and influential country was the United Kingdom followed by the United States. Although country from Europe and United States dominated the top 10 countries with the most publications by affiliated researchers, India, Malaysia and Pakistan is the country from Asia in the top 10.

Limitation: The current study has limitations; we only retrieved studies from Scopus and did not use other source such as Web of Science, Crossref, or PubMed Central. Finally, we did not use other analyses in VOSviewer, such as co-citation or co-authorship. Thus, we hope that bibliometric research on this topic will expand in terms of the databases used, the subject areas, and the analyses conducted in order to provide a broader overview of the issue.

Conclusion: Discourse on Good Governance was initiated with the publication of the first article (on the Scopus data base) in 2000, further expanded to 2021. However, based on the number of articles on this topic, the annual Scopus database indicates an improving trend since 2012. Topic such as Good Governance, Governance, and Evidence has become essentially prominent and has been widely discussed in the last two decades. The theme of

research on good governance related to local government could be interesting for future discussions. There are also opportunities to foster discussion about good governance in social science journals related to public administration. Finally, Europe dominated this field in terms of publications, while research from Asia on this topic remains limited, and further research is therefore necessary.

Conflict of Interest

No potential conflict of interest relevant to this article was reported.

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